

Drought resistance

Screening advanced breeding lines and germplasm for drought resistance under upland conditions

S. Pramanik and S. Gupta, Zonal Adaptive Research Station, Krishnagar, Nadia (W.B.), India

We screened 180 germplasm and advanced breeding lines involving parents of indica-japonica types under direct-seeded upland conditions at Krishnagar (gangetic alluvial zone) during the summer season (May-Jun). Short-duration lines are preferred for this season, since the monsoon generally appears about the third week of Jun. Short duration also gives room for the subsequent wet season crop.

Soil of the experimental plot had light medium texture with moderate sloping (susceptible to erosion). Soil had pH 7.2

Some characteristics of 11 entries screened under upland direct seeded situations. Krishnagar, India.

Designation	Height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Panicle length (cm)		Grain type ^a	Wt of single panicle (g)	Sheath blight score
			Mean	SD			
IR47701-79-B-14	94	75	20.0	1.36	MS	2.5	0
IR47701-79-B-1	93	73	24.6	2.16	MS	2.8	0
Milyang	91	67	15.0	1.25	SB	3.3	3
CNA4196	101	72	18.5	1.26	LS	3.7	5
IAC165	107	76	21.0	(0.16)	MS	3.7	0
CNA4746	104	68	20.5	1.32	LS	2.8	5
CNA4125	79	71	22.2	1.96	LB	1.8	5
GS529	110	67	23.0	1.21	LS	4.2	1
Dular (check)	99	67	19.5	2.31	MS	2.8	7
IET2223 (check)	93	75	23.0	1.27	MS	4.2	1
Rasi (check)	92	73	20.5	1.81	LB	3.0	6

^aMS = medium slender, SB = short bold, LS = long slender, LB = long bold.

and is deficient in N, organic matter, and phosphate. The crop was subjected to moisture stress at different growth stages, particularly during the seedling stage.

The experiment was laid out as a simple observational plot, with two 2-m rows/line (direct seeded), with 20 cm between rows.

Eight promising lines were identified

(see table). GS529 and Milyang have the same number of days to flowering as Dular, but GS529 has longer panicles and long slender grains, and is resistant to sheath blight. Panicle weight is high. Advanced breeding line RP47701-79-B-1, with 73 d to flowering and high resistance to sheath blight, is considered promising. □

Excess water tolerance

Promising breeding lines for submergence-prone and medium-deep rainfed lowland conditions

S. K. Sinha, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India; and D. J. Mackill, B. N. Singh, and M. M. Amante, Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

We evaluated 209 rice breeding lines and local and improved cultivars under two water regimes in the field at IRRI. Cultivars for both trials were sown 27 Jun and transplanted 27 Jul 1988.

In trial 1, entries were submerged gradually to a 60-cm water level 45 d after sowing (DAS). Water depth was maintained for 12 d, then gradually brought down to 25 cm for the remainder of the season. In trial 2, entries were submerged suddenly to 60

cm at 50 DAS, water depth was maintained for 8 d, then brought down to less than 10 cm.

Plant height before and after flooding were measured (tip of the longest leaf)

and percent survival calculated. Elongation was calculated as the difference in height before and after flooding.

Survival was 24.9% for trial 1 and 36.7% for trial 2. In trial 1, the correlation between survival and initial plant height was low, but significant (*r*

Entries with the highest survival in 2 field tests of performance^a under submergence. IRRI, 1988 wet season.

Breeding line	Survival (%)		Elongation (cm)		Submergence tolerance ^b	Mature height ^c (cm)	Days to maturity ^d
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2			
IR49830-26-1-2-1	65	75	29	19	3.0	130	140
IR51052-2-3-1-6	70	68	—	—	9.0	140	135
IR6370-K23-1	85	58	—	—	9.0	120	SEN
IR51053-10-2-3-2	59	68	—	—	8.0	140	130
IR49830-29-1-3-3-2	58	65	12	15	1.0	140	130
IR43470-7-3-5-1	54	58	25	5	3.0	115	130
BKNFR76106-16 (R ck)	11	89	17	19	6.6	105	120
IR43522-37-3-3-3	55	43	27	20	8.2	140	SEN
IR42 (susceptible check)	0	0	—	—	8.5	105	135

^aTrial 1 = slow submergence, trial 2 = rapid submergence. ^bAverage scores from screenhouse screening in tanks, compared with tolerant check FR13A. ^cAverage of field data. ^dSEN = photoperiod sensitive.